

Analysis of the Cultural Values of Robo-Robo as Local Wisdom toward Students' Social Interaction in Public Elementary Schools in Jongkat District

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the implementation of the Robo-Robo cultural tradition as local wisdom and its influence on students' social interaction in public elementary schools in Jongkat District, Mempawah Regency. The study uses a qualitative descriptive approach. Data were collected through observation, semi-structured interviews, and documentation involving principals, teachers, students, community leaders, and religious leaders. The research was conducted in three schools selected purposively, namely SDN 09 Wajok Hulu, SDN 08 Wajok Hilir, and SDN 03 Jongkat. Data analysis used an interactive model consisting of data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing, with validity tested through source and technique triangulation. The results show that the implementation of Robo-Robo varies across schools. SDN 09 integrates the tradition through Jepin dance performances, SDN 03 applies it through collective viewing of Robo-Robo history, and SDN 08 uses storytelling methods by teachers. Students' social interaction also varies. SDN 09 shows active and collaborative interaction, SDN 03 shows moderate interaction, and SDN 08 still shows partial individualistic tendencies. The study finds that Robo-Robo cultural values such as cooperation, togetherness, respect, and communication contribute to shaping students' social interaction. However, the impact depends on how the school integrates both understanding and direct practice. Schools that combine experiential and cognitive approaches show stronger social outcomes. The study concludes that Robo-Robo functions as an effective medium for social education when implemented consistently in school activities. The findings contribute to the development of culture-based education in strengthening students' social character.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Education, Elementary Students, Local Wisdom, Robo-Robo, Social Interaction.

INTRODUCTION

Local culture is an important basis in shaping the character and social identity of the community, including in elementary school students. Research shows the value of local culture contributes to the formation of empathy, cooperation, and social responsibility (Radeisyah et al., 2024). On the other hand, the development of globalization and modernization encourages changes in people's lifestyles. Data shows that the increase in the use of digital technology among school-age children has an impact on decreasing direct social interaction. This condition triggers the emergence of individualistic attitudes and reduced involvement in cultural-based social activities (Firmansyah et al., 2020). Therefore, strengthening local culture is a strategic step to maintain a balance between technological developments and the formation of students' social character.

One of the local cultures that still survives in West Kalimantan is the Robo-Robo tradition that developed in Jongkat District, Mempawah Regency. This tradition is part of the local wisdom of the Malay community which is carried out as a form of prayer for salvation, gratitude, and respect for ancestors (Satyaningrum et al., 2024). In its implementation, Robo-Robo involves the community collectively regardless of age, social status, or economic background. This activity creates an intense space for social interaction and provides an opportunity for children to learn the value of togetherness firsthand.

The social values contained in Robo-Robo include mutual cooperation, solidarity, mutual respect, and a sense of togetherness (Paradise, 2025). This value is relevant to the needs of character formation of elementary school students who are in the phase of social development. Children at this age begin to understand norms, rules, and social relationships in the surrounding environment. Through involvement in Robo-Robo, students not only cognitively get to know the culture, but also experience and practice social values in real life (Nurmansyah & Haris, 2022).

Schools have a role as the main environment in developing students' social interactions. Good interaction supports the learning process and forms positive social behaviors (Hayati, 2017). However, changes in modern life patterns affect the dynamics of interaction at school. Technology-based activities are more dominant than direct interactions. This has an impact on the low ability of communication, cooperation, and empathy between students. In this context, Robo-Robo culture can serve as an external stimulus that reinforces social interaction through tangible collective experiences.

Previous research has shown that involvement in local traditions has an effect on the formation of social character. Paradise (2025) found that participation in Robo-Robo improved students' empathy, cooperation, and communication skills. In addition, Setiawan (2022) identify the main values in Robo-Robo which are caring, affection, togetherness, and social resilience. This value has great potential to be integrated in the basic education process as part of strengthening character education.

Jongkat District is a relevant location for this research because the community still maintains the Robo-Robo tradition in the midst of modernization. Based on data from the Mempawah Regency Education Office in 2024, there are 22 State Elementary Schools in this region. However, only three schools consistently implement the Robo-Robo tradition in school activities, namely SDN 09 Wajok Hulu, SDN 08 Wajok Hilir, and SDN 03 Jongkat. These differences show a variety of policies and school commitments in integrating local culture into education.

This condition shows an opportunity to examine more deeply the relationship between the implementation of Robo-Robo culture and students' social interaction. The results of preliminary observations show that the existence of tradition is not always directly proportional to the quality of students' social interactions. Some students still show an individualistic attitude and low cooperation in school activities. This shows that the internalization of cultural values has not been optimally conducted and requires a more in-depth empirical study.

Previous research has mostly discussed Robo-Robo in terms of culture, history, and symbolic value in society. Studies examining its effect on the social interaction of elementary school students are still limited. Therefore, this study focuses on the analysis of how Robo-Robo cultural values affect students' social interactions in the context of formal education. The study also examines the reasons why only some schools consistently maintain this tradition.

This research combines the perspectives of education and cultural sociology. Its main focus is on the relationship between local cultural practices and students' social behavior in schools. The results of the research are expected to contribute to the development of local culture-based education models and become the basis for schools and policy makers in designing learning programs that integrate socio-cultural values.

Based on this description, this study is entitled "Analysis of Robo-Robo Cultural Values as Local Wisdom on Student Social Interaction in Jongkat District State Elementary School". This research is important to provide empirical evidence about the role of local culture in shaping students' social interactions. The integration of Robo-Robo values in education is expected to be able to strengthen the social character of students so that they are able to interact positively in the school environment and society

METHODOLOGY

This research method uses a qualitative approach with the aim of understanding in depth the implementation of Robo-Robo culture and its influence on students' social interaction in elementary school. Qualitative research is used because the focus of the study is not to measure numbers or test hypotheses, but to interpret the meaning of social phenomena that occur in the field. Researchers play the role of the main instrument that is directly involved in the data collection process through observation, interviews, and documentation. The data obtained were analyzed inductively to illustrate the relationship between Robo-Robo culture and students' social behavior in daily school life.

The form of this research is qualitative descriptive (Scott, 2024). This research aims to describe in detail the implementation of Robo-Robo culture as a local wisdom and the pattern of student social interaction that appears in school activities. The focus of the research lies in the processes, experiences, and meanings felt by the research subjects, thus producing systematic and in-depth descriptions according to real conditions in the field.

The research was carried out in Jongkat District, Mempawah Regency, West Kalimantan Province. This region was chosen because it still maintains the Robo-Robo tradition in the midst of social change. Based on data from the Mempawah Regency Education Office in 2024, there are 22 State Elementary Schools in Jongkat District. From this number, this study selected three schools that consistently implement the Robo-Robo culture, namely SDN 09 Wajok Hulu Village, SDN 08 Wajok Hilir Village,

and SDN 03 Jongak Village. The selection was carried out purposively by considering the active involvement of schools in the implementation of the Robo-Robo culture that is integrated into school activities. These three locations also have different geographical conditions with distances between villages of about 3 to 9 kilometers, thus providing a variation of relevant social contexts to be analyzed.

The data sources in this study consist of primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained directly from school principals, teachers, students, community leaders, and religious leaders involved in the implementation of the Robo-Robo culture. Informants were selected purposively considering their role and involvement in cultural activities and social interactions in schools. The composition of the informants included 1 school principal, 4 teachers, 6 students, 2 community leaders, and 2 religious leaders from the three schools that were the location of the research. Secondary data was obtained from school documents, activity archives, reports on the implementation of Robo-Robo, photos of activities, and relevant scientific references. This data is used to reinforce and complement the findings of the primary data.

Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation. Observations were carried out directly in the school environment to observe the implementation of Robo-Robo culture and students' social interactions, such as cooperation, communication, and social attitudes. The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner to dig up in-depth information from informants regarding their experiences and views regarding Robo-Robo culture. Documentation is used to collect supporting evidence in the form of photos of activities, school archives, and records of the implementation of cultural activities.

Data collection tools include observation guidelines, interview guidelines, and documentation guidelines. Observation guidelines are used to record phenomena observed systematically. Interview guidelines help researchers keep the focus of the questions according to the research objectives. Documentation guidelines are used to identify and collect documents relevant to the research.

Data analysis uses an interactive model consisting of three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawn. Data reduction is carried out by selecting and simplifying data that is relevant to the focus of the research. The presentation of data is carried out in the form of narrative descriptions to facilitate understanding of the patterns and relationships that emerge. Drawing conclusions is carried out by interpreting the meaning of the data to answer the focus of the research. The analysis process is carried out continuously during the research.

The validity of the data is checked through source triangulation and technical triangulation. Source triangulation is carried out by comparing data from school principals, teachers, students, community leaders, and religious leaders. Technical triangulation was carried out by comparing observation, interview, and documentation data. Both techniques are used to ensure the consistency and accuracy of the data so that the results of the research have a high level of confidence.

RESULTS

Implementation of Robo-Robo culture in Jongkat District at State Elementary Schools

The implementation of Robo-Robo culture in Jongkat District in three State Elementary Schools shows a variety of forms of activities, but still contains the same essence of values. Each school develops activities according to the learning conditions and approaches used. The results of the study show that the implementation of Robo-Robo is not only in the form of a joint ritual, but also combined with educational activities that support students' understanding of local culture.

At SDN 09 Wajok Hulu, the implementation of Robo-Robo was combined with Jepin dance activities performed by students. Jepin dance is part of Malay culture which is full of the value of togetherness and cohesiveness. The results of the observation showed that the students practiced and performed the dance in groups. This activity trains coordination, cooperation, and discipline between students. Social interaction is seen when students help each other in practice and appearance. There is no individual domination, all members of the group play an active role in maintaining the cohesiveness of the movement.

The results of interviews with teachers at SDN 09 show that the integration of Jepin dance aims to strengthen students' understanding of local culture through hands-on practice. The teacher stated that it is easier for students to understand the value of togetherness through artistic activities than theoretical explanations. The principal also emphasized that this activity is designed to build student confidence and solidarity. These findings are in line with research Paradise (2025) which states that active involvement in cultural activities enhances students' cooperative and social interaction skills.

Picture 1. Jepin dance activity by SDN 09 students

At SDN 03 Jongkat, the implementation of Robo-Robo was carried out through watching the history of Robo-Robo. The school shows videos or documentation explaining the origins and meaning of the tradition. The observation results showed that students followed the activity with focus and showed responses through discussions after the viewing. Social interaction comes in the form of questions and answers and sharing opinions between students.

Interviews with teachers show that this method is used to provide cognitive understanding to students before they engage in cultural activities directly. The teacher explained that students who understand the cultural background tend to appreciate the activities carried out more. Students also stated that they learned the meaning of Robo-Robo after watching together. These findings are in line with opinion Nurmansyah & Haris (2022) which emphasizes that the understanding of cultural values strengthens the process of internalization in the individual.

Picture 2. Activity to watch the history of Robo-Robo at SDN 03

At SDN 08 Wajok Hilir, the implementation of Robo-Robo was carried out through listening to the history of Robo-Robo delivered by teachers. This activity is in the form of direct narration that is packaged interactively. The results of the observations showed that students listened attentively and responded through questions. Interaction occurs between teachers and students, as well as between students in simple discussions.

Interviews with teachers showed that the story method was chosen because it was in accordance with the characteristics of elementary school students who are easier to understand through narrative. The teacher said that stories help students relate cultural values to everyday life. Students also stated that they understood the importance of togetherness and mutual respect after

listening to the story. These findings support research Setiawan (2022) which states that cultural values such as empathy and togetherness can be instilled through a narrative approach.

Picture 3. Listening to Robo-Robo stories at SDN 08

Based on the results of observations and interviews, the three schools showed different approaches in implementing the Robo-Robo culture. SDN 09 emphasizes cultural practices through dance, SDN 03 emphasizes understanding through visual media, and SDN 08 emphasizes instilling value through stories. Although they take different forms, these three approaches still lead to the same goal, which is to instill social values such as cooperation, togetherness, and mutual respect.

This finding is in line with the theory of local wisdom which states that culture can be transmitted through various forms of activities, both direct practice, visual media, and narrative. This variation of approach also shows that schools have an active role in adapting local culture into the educational process. Thus, the implementation of Robo-Robo in Jongkat District is not single, but develops in accordance with the learning strategies used by each school.

Social Interaction of Students at Jongkat District State Elementary School in Daily Life

The results of the study show that students' social interaction at Jongkat District State Elementary School is formed through learning activities, school activities, and daily relationships between students. These interactions reflect a pattern of relationships that involve communication, cooperation, and mutual respect. However, the level of quality of social interaction differs in each school and is influenced by the environment, habits, and students' involvement in social activities.

The results of observations at SDN 09 Wajak Hulu show that students have quite active social interactions. Students are used to working together in group activities, both in classroom learning and outside class activities. In learning activities, students can be seen helping each other complete assignments and discussing without waiting for the teacher's direction. The interaction that appears is open, students dare to express their opinions and respect the opinions of their peers. This condition shows that there is a two-way communication that is going well.

The results of interviews with teachers at SDN 09 showed that students who are often involved in cultural activities such as Robo-Robo tend to interact more easily. The teacher stated that students are more used to working in groups and show a mutually helpful attitude. Students also revealed that they feel comfortable interacting with friends because they often do activities together outside of formal learning.

At SDN 03 Jongkat, students' social interaction showed a fairly good pattern, but there were still some students who tended to be passive. The results of observations showed that in the discussion activities, some students actively spoke, while others only followed without participating directly. Interactions are more dominant in certain groups that have had previous closeness.

Interviews with teachers show that these differences are influenced by students' confidence and interaction habits. The teacher explained that students who have a better understanding of the local culture tend to be more confident in communicating. Meanwhile, students who are less involved in social activities show a tendency to be more passive. This shows that social experiences have an influence on students' ability to interact.

At SDN 08 Wajok Hilir, students' social interaction looks quite varied. The results of the observation showed that there was cooperation in certain activities, but individualistic attitudes were also found in some students. In group activities, there are still students who work alone without coordinating with friends. This condition shows that social interaction is not even among all students.

Interviews with teachers show that this difference is influenced by students' habits in using technology outside of school. The teacher stated that students who interact more through digital media tend to be less active in direct interactions. Students also admit that they play alone more often than interacting with friends outside of school hours.

These findings are in line with the theory of social interaction which states that interactions are formed through social contact and communication that take place continuously. According to Holy (2023) Social interaction at school is an important means of shaping students' social skills. In addition, Marisah et al., (2021) Stating that changes in modern lifestyles can decrease the quality of social interaction if they are not balanced with social activities that involve direct participation.

Based on the results of observations and interviews, the social interaction of students at Jongkat District State Elementary School showed variations influenced by social experiences, environment, and involvement in cultural activities. Schools that are more actively integrating social activities show better interaction than schools that involve students less in collective activities. This shows that students' social interactions are not formed automatically, but are influenced by experiences and a supportive social environment.

The Cultural Value of Robo-Robo as Local Wisdom for Students' Social Interaction at Jongkat District State Elementary School

The results of the study show that the cultural value of Robo-Robo has a role in shaping the social interaction of students at the State Elementary School of Jongkat District. The values that emerge in Robo-Robo activities include mutual cooperation, togetherness, mutual respect, empathy, and communication. This value is not only understood by students, but is also seen in daily behavior in the school environment. However, the level of internalization of grades differs from school to school and is influenced by the way it is implemented and the intensity of student involvement.

The results of observations at SDN 09 Wajok Hulu show that the value of togetherness and cooperation is seen in student interaction. Students involved in Jepin dance activities showed cohesiveness in group work. They help each other during practice and maintain harmony of movement while performing. In learning activities, students also show similar behavior by helping each other and actively discussing. This shows that the values practiced in cultural activities are carried over into learning activities.

The results of interviews with teachers showed that students who were active in Robo-Robo activities were more likely to cooperate and have a sense of responsibility towards the group. The teacher stated that cultural activities provide a direct experience that shapes students' social habits. The principal also emphasized that cultural integration in school activities has an impact on increasing positive interactions between students.

At SDN 03 Jongkat, the cultural value of Robo-Robo can be seen in the form of students' understanding of the importance of togetherness. The results of observations showed that students who participated in the activity of watching the history of Robo-Robo were able to re-explain the meaning of togetherness and mutual respect. In daily interactions, students begin to show an attitude of respect for their peers' opinions during discussions, although not all students actively participate.

Interviews with teachers show that understanding values through visual media helps students get to know the culture, but it requires reinforcement through practice. The teacher stated that students who only understood cognitively did not fully show behavioral changes. Students also revealed that they know the value of Robo-Robo, but have not always applied it in their daily activities.

At SDN 08 Wajok Hilir, the cultural value of Robo-Robo emerged through listening to historical stories delivered by teachers. The results of the observation showed that students understood values such as mutual respect and togetherness. However, in the practice of daily interaction, there are still students who do not cooperate in group activities. This shows that there is a gap between value understanding and application in behavior.

Interviews with teachers showed that the story approach was effective in instilling initial understanding, but it required follow-up activities to make these values a habit. The teacher stated that students need hands-on experience so that cultural values

can be internalized more strongly. Students also said that they understood the Robo-Robo story, but were not used to applying it in daily interactions.

These findings suggest that the cultural value of Robo-Robo has an effect on students' social interactions, but this influence depends on the form of implementation in schools. Schools that combine understanding and practice show stronger results than schools that emphasize only one aspect. This is in line with the opinion Sutrisno & Rofi'ah (2023) which states that the internalization of cultural values requires direct experience in social life. In addition, Wibowo (2024) explained that the values of empathy, togetherness, and care will be more effectively formed through active involvement in social activities.

In theory, this finding is also in accordance with the concept of local wisdom which states that culture functions as a guideline for behavior in society. The values contained in culture will form a pattern of interaction if practiced repeatedly. Lukitasari (2017) states that involvement in local traditions enhances individuals' communication and cooperation skills in a social environment.

Based on the results of observations and interviews, the cultural value of Robo-Robo has contributed to shaping students' social interactions in elementary school. These values can be seen in cooperative behavior, communication, and mutual respect. However, its effectiveness is influenced by the way the school implements the culture. The integration between understanding and practice is a major factor in strengthening the influence of cultural values on students' social interactions.

DISCUSSION

The findings show that the implementation of the Robo-Robo cultural tradition in public elementary schools in Jongkat District takes diverse forms while maintaining the same social values. Differences in implementation at SDN 09 Wajok Hulu, SDN 03 Jongkat, and SDN 08 Wajok Hilir indicate that schools play an active role in adapting local culture into educational activities. SDN 09 emphasizes practical engagement through the Jepin dance, SDN 03 uses visual media through historical presentations, and SDN 08 applies storytelling methods delivered by teachers. These variations are consistent with the concept of local wisdom, which suggests that cultural values can be transmitted through various media, both direct practice and cognitive approaches.

The practical approach implemented at SDN 09 produced stronger outcomes in shaping students' social interactions. Students involved in the Jepin dance demonstrated better cooperation, coordination, and communication. This finding supports the argument of Paradise (2025), who states that active participation in cultural activities enhances individuals' social abilities. Direct experience provides opportunities for students to practice values in concrete situations, making those values more likely to develop into habits.

Meanwhile, the cognitive approaches applied at SDN 03 and SDN 08 show that understanding cultural values does not always lead to behavioral change. Students were able to explain the meaning of Robo-Robo, but not all of them applied these values in their daily interactions. This finding is in line with Nurmansyah & Haris (2022), who emphasize that cultural understanding needs to be supported by social experience so that values can be internalized optimally. Setiawan (2022) also argues that values such as empathy and togetherness are more effectively developed through direct involvement than through explanation alone.

From the perspective of social interaction, the study found differences in the quality of interaction among schools. SDN 09 demonstrated active and collaborative interaction. SDN 03 showed fairly good interaction, although not evenly distributed among all students. SDN 08 still showed a tendency toward individualistic behavior among some students. These differences indicate that social interaction is influenced by the intensity of students' social experiences. Hayati (2017) states that social interaction in schools is formed through continuous processes of communication and cooperation. Students who frequently participate in collective activities have greater opportunities to develop social skills.

The influence of modernization was also evident in the findings. The use of digital technology and the decline of traditional social activities have affected students' interaction patterns. Some students showed a tendency to become more individualistic and less active in direct communication. This finding is consistent with Firmansyah et al., (2020) who argue that modern lifestyle changes can reduce the quality of social interaction if they are not balanced by cultural-based social activities.

The cultural values of Robo-Robo have been shown to contribute to the development of students' social interaction, particularly in the aspects of cooperation, communication, and togetherness. However, this influence does not occur automatically.

The findings indicate that schools that combine understanding with direct practice achieve more optimal results. This is in line with the theory of local wisdom, which states that cultural values shape behavior when they are practiced repeatedly in everyday life.

These findings strengthen the concept of local culture-based education, which positions culture as a source of learning. Robo-Robo functions not only as a tradition but also as a contextual medium for social learning. The integration of culture into school activities provides students with real experiences in building positive social relationships. Therefore, local culture plays a strategic role in supporting the development of students' social character in elementary schools.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that the Robo-Robo culture in Jongkat District State Elementary School does not only take place as a traditional activity, but has been integrated in educational activities with various forms of implementation. SDN 09 Wajok Hulu emphasizes practice through Jepin dance, SDN 03 Jongkat uses visual media through historical watching activities, and SDN 08 Wajok Hilir uses a narrative approach through teachers' stories. This difference shows that schools develop their own strategies in introducing local culture to students, but still lead to the same goal, which is the cultivation of social values.

The social interactions of students at all three schools show variation. Students at SDN 09 Wajok Hulu show more active and collaborative interaction. SDN 03 Jongkat showed quite good interaction but was not evenly distributed. SDN 08 Wajok Hilir still shows an individualistic tendency in some students. This condition is influenced by students' social experiences, school environment, and involvement in collective activities.

The cultural value of Robo-Robo has been proven to contribute to the formation of students' social interactions, especially in the aspects of cooperation, communication, and togetherness. However, these influences do not occur automatically. Schools that combine hands-on understanding and practice show stronger results than schools that emphasize only one approach. These findings reinforce the opinion that internalizing cultural values requires real experience in order to shape students' social behavior.

This research confirms that local culture can function as an effective social education medium if it is consistently integrated into school activities. Robo-Robo not only serves as a cultural heritage, but also as a means of forming students' social character in elementary school.

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